

REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AWARENESS OF ADOLESCENTS IN HARYANA: A STATUS STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The present study is undertaken to gauge the awareness level of adolescents from upper primary classes of co-educational, private unaided, English medium schools regarding reproductive health. The study explored the reproductive health awareness levels of 309 subjects from randomly selected ten schools of district Sonapat from the state of Haryana, India. The data was collected with the help of a self-administered, pre-tested, and validated questionnaire consisting of multiple-choice questions. The major themes around which the awareness was gauged comprised of adolescence and puberty, secondary sexual characteristics, the human reproductive system, and reproductive health. The study concludes that there is a lack of awareness among adolescents regarding the various aspects of reproductive health. Also, there is no significant difference reported in the awareness levels of male and female subjects.

Keywords: Awareness, Reproductive Health, Adolescents, Upper Primary

INTRODUCTION:

Adolescence- 'the phase of transition, ' from childhood to adulthood, embarks changes in physical, physiological, cognitive, emotional, and social aspects. The inquisitiveness is at its peak during this phase, and adolescents seek answers to the questions because they witness the changes in themselves and their peers. But, the question is, who talks about adolescence to the adolescents? Although the inclusion of health and sex education in the school curriculum has been controversial in the Indian context (Sharda & Watts, 2012), adolescence and its related topics have been included in the school curriculum at secondary and senior secondary level textbooks. Furthermore, different nomenclature has been assigned to address these topics as reproductive and sexual health, sexuality education, population education, family life education, and the latest one, comprehensive sexuality education. It may be addressed by any name, but when we talk about reproductive health, "it is about rights, informed choice, good health and well being of the human beings (Paul et al. 2011, p. 339)."

In the Indian context, parents expect the school to educate the kids about reproductive health, and the teachers still feel reluctant to discuss this topic in

classrooms, as evident in various studies (Mason et al., 2017, Ray et al. 2011). The mere inclusion of a few topics of reproductive health in the school curriculum does not guarantee that the adolescents are equipped with enough knowledge and awareness to cope with the changes they undergo during this phase. With reports of early sexual initiation (Iyer, 2015), sexual abuse, violence, and prevalence of risk-taking behavior among the youth pouring in from across the country (Tiwari et al. 2017, Nagalingam et al. 2016, Sivagurunathan et al. 2015), addressing reproductive health issues is much needed. Various researchers have assessed knowledge, attitude, and perceptions or practices (KAP) followed by adolescents across different parts of our country and have majorly reported a lack of knowledge regarding pubertal changes, conception and contraception, and other aspects of reproductive health (Gupta Tuli et al. 2017, Meena et al. 2015, Unni 2009, Gupta et al. 2004). The period of adolescence is generally divided into three phases: early (10-14 years), middle (15-16years), and late (17-19 years) adolescence. Most of the policies that are drafted and research work that is undertaken generally targets middle and late adolescence. Very young adolescents from the age group 10-14 years are 'understudied'; hence, not much is known about them

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(UNFPA 2006, Lane et al., 2017). The present paper attempts to gauge the awareness level of upper primary school students from CBSE affiliated schools from Sonipat district of Haryana regarding reproductive health.

NEED OF THE STUDY:

Studies conducted across different districts of Haryana like Rohtak, Ambala, Faridabad districts reveal low information levels regarding reproductive health among adolescents (Goel & Mittal 2010, Kumar et al. 2017, Jadon 2018). The adolescent girls of Haryana suffer from anemia, malnutrition as well as sexually transmittable infections, and unwanted pregnancies (Yadav et al., 2015). A cross-sectional study conducted in Haryana revealed smoking and drug usage among boys and girls (Wadhwa et al., 2018). A recent study of the impact of the Adolescence Education Programme in 25 government schools of Sonipat District reports a substantial change in the awareness level of class ten adolescents (Dogra 2017). However, there has been no study covering very young adolescents in the age group of 10-14 years. Amidst so many government initiatives like 'Beti Bachao Beti Padhao' and 'Rashtriya Kishore Swasthya Karyakaram' implemented in Haryana, the present study explores the reproductive health awareness of very young adolescents to know their unmet needs and cater to the same.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Nesan et al. (2021), through their KAP study about sex education, reported a lack of overall knowledge regarding sexual health, STD, and reproduction. Gundi & Subramanyam (2019) underlined a lack of communication on this topic to the extent that boys' queries on menstruation were generally overlooked. Also, taboos were prevalent; girls were reluctant to discuss their menstrual problems and reported anxiousness before menarche. Phulambrikar et al. (2018) explored KAP regarding reproductive and sexual health and found that more than half of the participants lacked basic knowledge about the female reproductive tract. Harshana and Kapoor (2018) found partial knowledge about secondary sexual characteristics in their study on boys. More than half of the participants lacked knowledge about the sequence of development of secondary sexual characteristics. In a study by R. Gupta & Singh (2017), menstruation was reported as a period of disturbance by adolescent girls as they were perturbed by the changing body shape, hair growth, acne, obesity which led to low self-esteem among them. In their systematic

review, Van Eijk et al. (2016) concluded a lack of awareness regarding menstruation before menarche among the majority in India. The review further stated that lack of awareness is more prevalent in Northern India, and mothers were the primary source of information for most girls. As evident from the review, most studies focus on older adolescents' knowledge, attitude, and perceptions. There is a dearth of studies on 10-14 years old adolescents, especially in Haryana. Hence, the present study attempts to assess the awareness level possessed by very young adolescents studying in private unaided schools of district Sonipat, Haryana.

OBJECTIVE:

To gauge the awareness of the adolescents studying in upper primary classes regarding various aspects of adolescent reproductive health.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted across CBSE affiliated English medium co-educational schools of Sonipat district of Haryana. The data was collected from 350 subjects from age group 10-14 years from December 2019 to February 2020. The data collected for this study is a part of a research work undertaken by the author where a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design is adopted.

Out of the ninety CBSE affiliated schools as per the UDISE report for the previous session, 2018-19 in the district, twenty-two were randomly selected. The permission was obtained from ten schools, and the sample comprised of students from class eight. The data was collected through a self-developed and validated questionnaire consisting of multiple-choice questions. The twenty-nine items in the tool addressed four themes: Adolescence and puberty; secondary sexual characteristics and role of hormones; human reproductive system; and reproductive health. After ascertaining validity through experts, the tool's reliability (KR 20) was calculated to be .78 through a pilot.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

After receiving due permission for the conduct of the study, the investigator visited the schools as per the time allocated. A brief introduction of the study and the reason for data collection was communicated to the subjects. Also, they were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. The guidelines for filling up the questionnaire were also provided. Each item in the questionnaire had four options, out of which only one was correct, and each question carried one mark. The

subjects were allowed 35 minutes to fill up the questionnaire. The sheets were collected, coded, and checked as per the key, and data was entered into MS Excel for further analysis. Out of 350 subjects, after data cleaning, a data set of 309 was available, which was analyzed using descriptive statistics, frequency, percentage, and t-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The majority of the sample comprised 13-year-old subjects, and the average age of the subjects was 12.97 years. The analysis reveals that mean of the scores on the questionnaire is 13.72. This indicates that out of 29 questions, subjects could score an average of 13.72, which is 47.3% of the total score (29). In comparison, the males' mean score (n=162) is

found slightly higher than the females' (n=147). F-test was applied on the test scores of the males (mean=14.00, variance= 17.91) and females (mean=13.40, variance= 16.44) to ascertain any significant difference in the variance. The results of the F-test reveal that p value= 0.299 for F=1.08 (df= 161, 146), thus concluding homogeneity of variance between the scores obtained by male subjects and female subjects. The t-test for equal variances was then applied. The output revealed t-statistic=1.265, df=307, p>0.05, thereby concluding no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female subjects. The data set was further categorized on their scores obtained into three categories: Low, Inadequate, and Adequate as described in the table below:

Table: Categorical assignment of subjects

Awareness Level	Score Criteria	Total		Males		Females	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Low	<= 10	64	20.7%	30	18.5%	34	23.1%
Inadequate	11- 19	215	69.6%	114	70.4%	101	68.7%
Adequate	>= 20	30	9.7%	18	11.1%	12	8.2%

As revealed by the table, around 20.7% of the subjects scored low; they had a score below 33.3%. Around 69.6% of the subjects had an average score. Only 9.7% of the subjects had a high score (i.e., above 66.67% of the total score). Thus, in a nutshell, it can

be inferred that the adolescents of upper primary classes are inadequately aware of reproductive health, with 90% of subjects in possession of inadequate information regarding various aspects of reproductive health, graphically depicted in the figure below.

Figure: Distribution of subjects based on awareness level

The graphical representation gives a comparative bird eye view for the distribution of subjects into three categories. Overall, a vast majority of subjects (90.3%) possess either inadequate or low levels of awareness regarding adolescent reproductive health. These results indicate the knowledge gaps prevalent among adolescents regarding adolescent reproductive health. Thus, we infer that adolescents are

neither well informed nor aware of Adolescent Reproductive Health at this crucial stage of their lives. The same lacunae in knowledge among the adolescent population have been reported in the studies by Singh et al. (2021), who reported 92.5% had inadequate awareness level, Jadon (2018), who reported a lack of reproductive health awareness among boys. The results are in corroboration with Srivastava and Singh (2017)

and Patanwar & Sharma (2013), who reported poor knowledge about pubertal changes and reproductive health.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS:

If adolescents are equipped with age-appropriate knowledge about reproductive health, they develop a better understanding of their own body, adapt well to the changes, and develop a positive and healthy outlook towards life in general. Educating them about reproductive health in the early years will instill confidence in them to step forward in pride. We need to adopt a holistic approach for the overall well-being of adolescents and eradicate the myths and misconceptions regarding many reproductive health issues like menstruation and masturbation. We should not neglect the needs of very young adolescents. Instead, we must supplement them with accurate and scientific information regarding reproductive health. The government initiatives must cater to the diverse needs of the heterogeneous adolescent population rather than giving a comprehensive 'one size fits all package.' Instead of following the traditional approach of training the teachers or peers and then delivering the programs, we can use technology to supplement them with tailored programs that cater to adolescents' individualistic needs.

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